

Monitoring Industry 4.0 Applications for Security and Safety Standard Compliance

Ani Bicaku^{1,3}, Christoph Schmittner², Markus Tauber¹ and Jerker Delsing³

¹University of Applied Sciences Burgenland - Eisenstadt, Austria

²Austrian Institute of Technology - Vienna, Austria

³Luleå University of Technology - Luleå, Sweden

Abstract—In Industry 4.0 independent entities shall inter-operate to allow flexible and customized production. To assure the parties that individual components are secured to inter-operate, we investigate automated standard compliance. The standard compliance is defined based on given sets of safety, security and organizational requirements from which are derived measurable indicator points. Those reflect configurations of systems recommended by security, safety or legally relevant standards and guidelines including organizational aspects, which help to demonstrate the state of compliance. We propose in this paper an initial approach to automate such assessment when components are inter-operating with each other by using a monitoring and standard compliance verification framework. This will assure the parties that services or devices within their organizations operate in a secure and standard compliant way, without compromising the underlying infrastructure.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for flexible and customized production brings new challenges to the existing manufacturing systems. To address these challenges, lots of research efforts have been conducted to pave the way for the fourth industrial revolution, known as Industry 4.0, which aims to optimize production by sharing physical and cyber resources [1]. This may also include inter-operation between individual companies or legal entities within large enterprises. Existing technologies, such as Internet of Things (IoT), System of Systems (SoS), Cyber Physical Systems (CPS), cloud computing and Service Oriented Architectures (SOA), allow for such inter-operation already [2]. Nevertheless, it is important for entities to assure that the components inter-operate in safe and secure manner.

In the industrial environments, the fulfillment of security, safety and legal requirements of devices autonomously communicating with each other plays a fundamental role. Security incidents consequences can be in different areas or dimensions, such as interruption or modification of an operational process, or even sabotage with intention to cause harm. Manipulating or interrupting such systems could also affect safety, which can have consequences such as environmental damage, injury or loss of life [3]. Security and safety incidents are tolerated more easily if one can show that they occurred despite the affected IT system being compliant with all applicable security regulations. This can be achieved via manual audits, which are often based on existing standards and guidelines.

The new technologies and requirements of Industry 4.0 create a new demand for standardization, which plays a key

role in improving security and safety across different regions and communities. In the last years, different standard organizations have been established, mostly initiated from industry, and have published various standards in different fields and topics. Despite the extensive research [4], [5], [6], and a considerable number of widely accepted security, safety and legal standards, existing approaches are insufficient to meet the requirements imposed by challenges and issues in Industry 4.0.

In order to address the aforementioned concerns, we propose an initial approach to automatically verify standard compliance by using a monitoring and standard verification framework, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: High level view of standard compliance verification

The monitoring and standard compliance framework, built on our previous work [7], uses an Evidence Gathering Mechanism (EGM) to collect evidence from a number of components in the target system based on a set of measurable indicator points (MIPs). The MIPs, categorized in measurable security indicators (MSI), measurable safety indicators (MSFI) and other organizational indicators related to legal (MSLI), are extracted from existing standards and guidelines to address target system specific requirements (e.g. access control systems for the production line should be resistant against side-channel attacks). This information is then used to define if the target system is operating in a secure and standard compliant way.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews widely used security and safety standards/best practice guidelines and research on monitoring and compliance. Section III presents the overall architecture of the framework and the standard compliance verification approach. In Section IV a representative set of MIPs is provided and we conclude our work in Section V.

II. RELATED WORK

To enable the global usability of the products and systems, standardization in the industrial environment is of utmost importance. The new technologies and requirements of Industry 4.0 create a new demand for standardization, which plays a key role in improving security, safety and legal aspects across different regions and communities. In the last years, several standard organizations have published various standards in different fields and topics. Cybersecurity Coordination Group (CSCG), EU Network and Information Security (ENISA), The European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) are some of the most popular standardization bodies.

ISO 27000-series standards [8], also known as ISMS Family of Standards, deal with different area of information security including requirements, implementation guidelines and risk management. They cover almost all the aspects of technology and business addressing cyber-security, privacy, confidentiality and other aspects of security issues by providing updates of the latest technologies and threats.

ISO/IEC 15408 [9], known as Common Criteria (CC), provides a framework where can be specified the security functionality of IT products and the assurance requirements during a security evaluation. The CC evaluation is divided in three parts. The CC part 1, provides general concepts of IT security and defines the core concept of a Target of Evaluation (TOE). The CC part 2 - Security functional components, includes a catalog of security functional components and categorize them in a hierarchical order based on families, classes and components. The CC part 3 - Security assurance components, defines the assurance requirements of the TOE expressed in a Protection Profile (PP) or a Security Target (ST). Also, it includes the Evaluation Assurance Levels (EAL) that defines the scale for measuring assurance for each component of the TOE. Nevertheless, CC has only focused on security evaluation without considering safety or legal aspects.

IoT Security Compliance Framework [10] is an assurance guideline for organizations used to provide a structured evidence to demonstrate conformance with best practice guidelines. The compliance scheme in this document is based on risk profiles for different systems and environments including: (i) business processes, (ii) devices and aggregation points, (iii) networking and (iv) cloud and server elements. The compliance process is based on a set of requirements of organizations and products by defining five classes of compliance on a scale from 0 to 4. The compliance process determines also the levels of confidentiality, integrity and availability (C-I-A) for each compliance class. In order to apply the required level of security and to maintain the level of trust for IoT systems, each requirement includes an ID, the compliance class, and the applicability category.

A recent review of the literature on IoT security and trust is conducted in [11]. The authors evaluate relevant existing solutions related to IoT security, privacy and trust. The existing

work is analyzed based on topics such as authentication, access control, privacy, policy enforcement, trust, confidentiality and secure middleware. In this survey they present the main research challenges in IoT security, the most relevant solutions and arise questions for future research related to security and trust in IoT. This overview shows that available solutions involve different technologies and standards, but a unified vision for security requirements is still missing.

Julisch [12] introduces the compliance problem by focusing on security requirements. In this work, security is the state of being safe from threats and the security compliance is the evidence (assurance) that a given set of requirements is met, which can be security requirements or other security mechanisms imposed by standards. He underlines that, in order to narrow the gap between academia and industry, it is necessary to focus more research on the question of security compliance to help organizations to comply with best practices guidelines and standards.

For safety the basic safety standard is IEC 61508 [13] "Functional Safety of Electrical / Electronic / Programmable Electronic Safety-Related System". This standard is developed as a domain independent standard which can be adapted for all domains without a domain-specific standard. The process industry developed, based on IEC 61508, IEC 61511 [14] "Functional safety - Safety instrumented systems for the process industry sector". Such a domain specific instantiation is mainly developed to consider peculiarities from a specific domain. For the industrial sectors both standards are relevant. Compliance to both standards was mostly evaluated during the design time [15], [16]. It was assumed that safety-critical systems are stable and compliance can be completely checked during design time. Due to Industry 4.0 and the goal of increased production flexibility there is an increasing need to check compliance also during run-time. Existing approaches utilize mainly concepts from contract-based development [17]. This assumes that the basic blocks of a safety-critical system will stay the same and are assessed during design-time. Contracts are then used to check the compliance of different system compositions based on pre-checked blocks [18]. While such approaches allow to shift a part of the safety assessment towards run-time, there is still the challenge that with flexible and configurable systems components need to check if they are still compliant with their respective safety standard.

Although the produced guidelines and scientific work help users to address industrial requirements, more standard compliance measurements are needed.

There are various frameworks and platforms supporting monitoring of CPS and IoT. Several approaches and prototypes are presented both, in literature [19], [20], [21] and in scope of research projects such as Cumulus, NGcert, SECCRIT etc. However, there is no generally accepted method that allows mapping the security and safety compliance. In this context, the proposed monitoring and standard compliance verification framework advances the state of the art by considering security, safety and organizational related to legal aspects without compromising the underlying infrastructure.

III. MONITORING AND STANDARD COMPLIANCE VERIFICATION FRAMEWORK

Standard compliance is the adherence with a given set of security and safety requirements, represented by measurable metrics, on the use and configuration of systems or any other security, safety or legal mechanism. These measurable metrics should be imposed by standardized bodies to make each system, device or application comply with the standards.

To assure that the system is operating in a secure and standard compliant manner a monitoring module is needed, which is responsible for gathering all the required measurements. Thus, in this work we present a monitoring and standard compliance verification framework, which has been design to support different use cases and viewpoints that should be considered and researched in Industry 4.0.

The monitoring and standard compliance verification framework, illustrated in Figure 2, allows to gather security, safety and legal evidence from the target system into a structured way (e.g. MSI, MSFI, MSSSI). The architecture of the framework has a pluggable and expendable architecture allowing easy adaptation to constantly analyze and monitor the status of the system or components of the system. It is able to monitor a large number of measurable metrics for different CPPS components by aggregating, scheduling, storing, retrieving and analyzing the monitoring data to provide standard compliance verification.

Fig. 2: Monitoring and standard compliance verification framework used to measure, aggregate, schedule, store, retrieve and analyze the monitoring data to provide standard compliance

The monitoring and standard compliance verification framework is composed of four main modules, including Monitoring Agents (MA), Evidence Gathering Mechanism (EGM), Compliance and the Target System (TS). The TS represents a system or component of a system that will be monitored by monitoring tool plugins or customized scripts.

A. Monitoring components

1) *Monitoring Agents (MA)*: The MA module is used to gather data from the TS and should allow the integration of different pluggable monitoring agents (MA_n) from different monitoring tool plugins (e.g., Nagios plugin [22], Ceilometer plugin [23], Zabbix plugin [24], etc.) and customized scripts.

2) *Evidence Gathering Mechanism (EGM)*: The EGM module is designed to acquire, store and analyze security, safety and legal related evidence [7]. It manages the incoming data from the monitoring agents and decides when/what data to send to the Compliance module by using a writing buffer. It make possible the mapping of the measurable metrics and their values with the standards to provide the necessary information for the compliance module. The EGM module consists of:

a) *Monitoring Agent Manager*: The Monitoring Agent Manager is the only contact point between the EGM module and the MA_n. It is responsible for organizing the MA_n based on the configurations and uses a Monitoring Scheduler to provide the run-time of each plugin in the corresponding component.

b) *Monitoring Source Standard*: The Monitoring Source Standard provides for each defined measurable metric the source from which standard/best practice guideline the metric is extracted. By mapping the MIPs to the specific standard, the compliance module can cross-check if the specific metric has been monitored in the target system.

c) *Bitwise MIPs Representation*: The Bitwise MIPs Representation module represents every MIP by a number, which can be converted to binary and operated on by a computer.

The EGM module gathers the monitoring data in a column structure based on the MIPs (MSI, MSFI, and MSSSI). For each MIP the following information is provided: (i) metric ID, (ii) value of the metric, which can be a binary value, true/false value, etc and (iii) the source based on the standard/best practice guideline from where the metric is extracted. A representative set of the information provided by the EGM module is shown in Figure 3.

MIPs	Value TS_A	Value TS_B	S1	S2	S3
MSI-1,1	1	1	⊗		
MSI-2,1	0	1		⊗	
MSFI-1,1	1	1			⊗
MSFI-2,1	0	1			⊗
MSSI-1,1	0	1			⊗
MSSI-2,1	1	1			⊗

EGM
 + MSI
 + MSSSI
 + MSFI

MIP - Measurable Indicator Point
 MSI - Measurable Security Indicator
 MSFI - Measurable Safety Indicator
 MSSSI - Measurable SLA Indicator
 TS_n - Target System n
 Sn - Standard n

Fig. 3: A representative set of the information provided by the EGM module

The information provided by the EGM module is used as an input for the Compliance module for further analysis.

B. Standard Compliance Verification

In Industry 4.0 large monolithic organisations are moving towards multi-stakeholder cooperations, where cooperation is fostered by market requirements such as sustainable, flexible, efficient, competitive and customized production [1]. Despite the benefits, this brings new challenges in terms of security, safety and legal related issues. Thus, it is of utmost importance to assure that independent entities inter-operate with each other in a secure and standard compliant manner, without compromising the underlying infrastructure.

In this paper we present an initial approach for standard compliance verification. The Compliance module is responsible for assuring that the system is operating in a secure and standard compliant manner driven by the input provided by the EGM module. The compliance depends on a set of MIPs, which are extracted from a number of widely used standards and best practice guidelines to address the target system specific requirements. Thus, in order to measure standard compliance one has to consider a set of MIPs and a set of standards, since a dynamic mix of new technologies, regulations and interactions of different organizations are involved. However, it is not easy to extract metrics for security, safety and legal related issues [25], [26], since the indirect relationship and the dependability between them have to be considered as well. In the following section we present a representative set of MIPs for a specific target system and show how such a metric can be described.

Fig. 4: Security standard compliance verification

To show the standard compliance verification approach, we have considered only MSIs. However, the same approach applies also for MSFIs and MSSIs. Each MSI extracted from a standard is monitored using monitoring agents in the corresponding component of the target system. The monitoring data are then gathered by the EGM module, which is responsible for making them readable for the Compliance module. So, the EGM sends to the Compliance module for each MSI the source from which the metric is extracted and a binary value 1 or 0 that indicates if the metric is fulfilled or not. Depending on

the specific target system requirements the Compliance module assigns to each MSI a weight value to indicate the importance in the range $[0, 1]$.

After gathering all the required evidence from the EGM module, the Compliance module first verifies the compliance [%] for a single standard as the ratio between the sum of each MSI measured value multiplied by its weight value and the total number of metrics per standard as shown in equation 1. Then it verifies the total compliance [%] as the ratio between the sum of each standard compliance and the total number of selected standards, as shown in equation 2.

$$MSI_compliance_{(j)}[\%] = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n MSI_{i,j} \omega_{i,j}}{n} 100\% \quad (1)$$

$$MSI_compliance[\%] = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m compliance_{(j)}}{m} 100\% \quad (2)$$

where:

n	total number of metrics per standard
m	total number of standards
$MSI_{i,j}$	measured value of "i" security metric from "j" standard
$\omega_{i,j}$	weight value of "i" security metric from the "j" standard

Introduction of Compliance Levels

In order to apply an appropriate level of security and safety standard compliance to a component or system depending on the requirements, four compliance levels [0-3] are arbitrary defined:

Compliance Level	MIPs		
	MSI	MSFI	MSSI
Level 0	basic	basic	basic
Level 1	basic	basic	high
	high	basic	basic
Level 2	basic	high	high
	high	basic	high
Level 3	high	high	basic
	high	high	high

TABLE I: Arbitrary compliance levels based on MIPs

The compliance levels, shown in table I, depend on the standard compliance verification for MSIs, MSFIs and MSSIs, where as *basic* is defined the compliance in the range $[0\%, 50\%]$ and as *high* is defined the compliance in the range $[50\%, 100\%]$.

- **Compliance Level 0** indicates that the compliance of all three MIP groups is basic
- **Compliance Level 1** indicates that at least the compliance of one MIP group is high
- **Compliance Level 2** indicates that at least the compliance of two MIP groups is high
- **Compliance Level 3** indicates that the compliance of all three MIP groups is high

IV. A REPRESENTATIVE SET OF MIPs FOR THE MONITORING AND STANDARD COMPLIANCE VERIFICATION FRAMEWORK

This section provides illustrative metrics that should be considered in an Industry 4.0 application scenario with the goal to address the requirements of access control systems for the production line. In that regard, the IEC 62443-3-3 (Industrial communication networks - Network and system security - System security requirements and security levels) [27] provides technical control system fundamentals requirements for industrial automation and control system capability, where we have selected three MSIs to show how each MSI is documented and monitored. Also, the IEC 61508-3 (Functional Safety of Electrical/Electronic/Programmable Electronic Safety-related Systems) [28], is the basic safety standard and intended as a kind of umbrella standard by various industries to provide their own standards and guidelines, from which are selected two MSFIs as representative examples.

A. Use Case

In order to extract MIPs, which can be used to evaluate the approach described in the previous section, we consider the use case depicted in Figure 5, from an ongoing research project addressing a secure end-to-end communication in CPPS [29].

Fig. 5: CPPS end-to-end communication use case

To provide device management as a service, data is transmitted between devices (M1, M2, and M3), processed and sent to a private cloud for further processing and analysis. The communication protocol used between the edge devices, the IIoT components, and the cloud backend is the MQTT protocol, designed to be lightweight, flexible and simple to implement. In the production environment, the new industrial devices are already able to communicate using state of the art IIoT protocols, such as MQTT. However, this is not the case if a legacy device wants to establish a connection with the IIoT gateway. In this case, a translator system is needed to translate the device protocol into MQTT [30]. In such scenario, with different decentralized CPPS components, condition reports to the overall system are important. In order to observe the system behavior, several components can be monitored, including industrial devices, IIoT gateways and cloud services.

Once the requirements have been identified and the standards/best practice guidelines have been examined if they address or not the specific requirement, the next step is to identify measurable indicator points. Based on this use case and the access control requirements, we define a set of

representative MSIs and MSFIs extracted from security and safety standards. For each MIP is provided: (i) an ID, (ii) the source and the definition based on the standards and best practice guidelines, (iii) possible monitoring solutions and (iv) a monitoring value.

B. MSIs: Measurable Security Indicators

- **MSI-1.1:** Secure identification and authentication
 - *Source:* IEC 62443-3-3
 - *Definition:* The client and the server identify each other and assure their identities via secure log-on
 - *Monitoring Plugin:* Can be monitored with Nagios monitoring agent, which checks the configuration of the used protocol (or indeed any other client/server authentication method) to make sure that it uses a secure communication protocol.
 - *Monitoring Value:* True/False
- **MSI-2.1 :** Strength of password-based authentication
 - *Source:* IEC 62443-3-3
 - *Definition:* The system shall be configurable by providing a degree of complexity such as minimum length, variety of characters and password rotation.
 - *Monitoring Plugin:* Can be implemented by performing checks on the PAM (Pluggable Authentication Module) to verify if a minimum length or complexity of passwords and password rotation is enabled.
 - *Monitoring Value:* True/False
- **MSI-3.1 :** Concurrent session control
 - *Source:* IEC 62443-3-3
 - *Definition:* The system shall restrict the maximum number of concurrent sessions per system account or system type.
 - *Monitoring Plugin:* A script can be developed which checks `sshd_config` or `pam_limits` configuration.
 - *Monitoring Value:* True/False

C. MSFIs: Measurable Safety Indicators

- **MSFI-1.2 :** Time-triggered architecture
 - *Source:* IEC 61508-3, Table A-2, Group 13
 - *Definition:* : Ensure that the system complies with the safety timing requirements
 - *Monitoring Plugin:* Can be checked via Nagios, send test packet to system and check if response time is inside allowed parameters. If Nagios is running on a separate system this achieves medium diagnostic coverage (based on IEC 61508-2). If the systems sends regular information about logical status high diagnostic coverage is achievable
 - *Monitoring Value:* Response time
- **MSFI-2.2 :** Techniques and measures for error detection
 - *Source:* IEC 61508-3, Table A-18
 - *Definition:* Ensure that system modifications are protected against erroneous
 - *Monitoring Plugin:* Check that system modifications require a password

– Monitoring Value: True/False

As illustrated in Figure 2, the monitoring agents defined for each MIP, will gather data from the target system (in this case the end-to-end communication use case) and will provide for the EGM the necessary information if the metric is fulfilled or not. The Compliance module maps the monitored metric with the corresponding standard and calculate the compliance [%] based on equation 2. The result will then be used to define the compliance level [0-3] of the system as shown in table I.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have presented a monitoring and standard compliance verification framework for Industry 4.0 application scenarios with the aim to provide an automated standard compliance. The standard compliance is defined based on a set of MIPs extracted from existing standards and best practice guidelines. The MIPs are monitored in the target system using monitoring agents and the monitoring data are then used by the EGM to make them readable for the compliance module.

To give an example on how such an approach will work, we have extracted a representative set of MSIs and MSFIs motivated by the requirements provided from an ongoing research project use case. We have provided the information on how the MSIs and MSFIs can be measured by either existing monitoring tool plugins or customized scripts.

As part of our future work, we will further analyze other security and safety standards that are relevant to the industrial environment to extract additional MSIs, MSFIs and MSSIs. We will also investigate how the information provided by the monitoring and standard compliance verification framework can be integrated in the Arrowhead Framework e.g., Arrowhead Test Tool (ATT) [31], which enables the possibility to test producer and consumer interfaces for the Arrowhead services.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The work has been performed in the project Power Semiconductor and Electronics Manufacturing 4.0 (SemI40), grant agreement n°692466. The project is co-funded by grants from Austria, Germany, Italy, France, Portugal and Electronic Component Systems for European Leadership Joint Undertaking.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Delsing, "Iot automation: Arrowhead framework," 2017.
- [2] A. W. Colombo, T. Bangemann, and S. Karnouskos, "Imc-aesop outcomes: Paving the way to collaborative manufacturing systems," in *Industrial Informatics (INDIN), 2014 12th IEEE International Conference on*. IEEE, 2014, pp. 255–260.
- [3] C. Schmittner, Z. Ma, and E. Schoitsch, "Combined safety and security development lifecycle," in *Industrial Informatics (INDIN), 2015 IEEE 13th International Conference on*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 1408–1415.
- [4] E. Jonsson, "Towards an integrated conceptual model of security and dependability," in *Availability, Reliability and Security, 2006. ARES 2006. The First International Conference on*. IEEE, 2006, pp. 8–pp.
- [5] D. Basin, F. Klaedtke, and S. Müller, "Monitoring security policies with metric first-order temporal logic," in *Proceedings of the 15th ACM symposium on Access control models and technologies*. ACM, 2010.
- [6] L. Hayden, *IT Security Metrics: A Practical Framework for Measuring Security & Protecting Data*. McGraw-Hill Education Group, 2010.
- [7] A. Bicaku, S. Balaban, M. G. Tauber, A. Hudic, A. Mauthe, and D. Hutchison, "Harmonized monitoring for high assurance clouds," in *Cloud Engineering Workshop (IC2EW), 2016 IEEE International Conference on*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 118–123.
- [8] G. Disterer, "Iso/iec 27000, 27001 and 27002 for information security management," *Journal of Information Security*, vol. 4, p. 92, 2013.
- [9] C. C. Consortium *et al.*, "Common criteria (aka cc) for information technology security evaluation (iso/iec 15408), 2013," *Website: http://www.commoncriteriaportal.org*.
- [10] R. Atoui, J. Bennett, S. Cook, P. Galwas, P. Gupta, J. Haine, H. Trevor, C. Hills, R. Marshall, M. John, K. Munro, I. Phillips, D. Purves, C. Robbins, D. Rogers, C. Shaw, R. Shepherd, and C. Shire, "Iot security compliance framework," *IoT Security Foundation*, 2016.
- [11] S. Sicari, A. Rizzardi, L. A. Grieco, and A. Coen-Porisini, "Security, privacy and trust in internet of things: The road ahead," *Computer Networks*, vol. 76, pp. 146–164, 2015.
- [12] K. Julisch, "Security compliance: the next frontier in security research," in *Proceedings of the 2008 workshop on New security paradigms*. ACM, 2009, pp. 71–74.
- [13] D. J. Smith and K. G. Simpson, *Safety Critical Systems Handbook: A Straight forward Guide to Functional Safety, IEC 61508 (2010 EDITION) and Related Standards, Including Process IEC 61511 and Machinery IEC 62061 and ISO 13849*. Elsevier, 2010.
- [14] K. Bond, "Iec 61511-functional safety: Safety instrumented systems for the process industry sector," in *Annual Symposium on Instrumentation for the Process Industries*, vol. 57, 2002, pp. 33–40.
- [15] M. Lloyd and P. Reeve, "Iec 61508 and iec 61511 assessments-some lessons learned," 2009.
- [16] R. K. Panesar-Walawege, M. Sabetzadeh, L. Briand, and T. Coq, "Characterizing the chain of evidence for software safety cases: A conceptual model based on the iec 61508 standard," in *Software Testing, Verification and Validation (ICST), 2010 Third International Conference on*. IEEE, 2010, pp. 335–344.
- [17] A. Sangiovanni-Vincentelli, W. Damm, and R. Passerone, "Taming dr. frankenstein: Contract-based design for cyber-physical systems," *European journal of control*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 217–238, 2012.
- [18] D. Schneider and M. Trapp, "Conditional safety certificates in open systems," in *Proceedings of the 1st workshop on critical automotive applications: robustness & safety*. ACM, 2010, pp. 57–60.
- [19] M. T. Lazarescu, "Design of a wsn platform for long-term environmental monitoring for iot applications," *IEEE Journal on Emerging and Selected Topics in Circuits and Systems*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 45–54, 2013.
- [20] Y. Liu, Y. Yang, X. Lv, and L. Wang, "A self-learning sensor fault detection framework for industry monitoring iot," *Mathematical problems in engineering*, vol. 2013, 2013.
- [21] S. Tennina, M. Bouroche, P. Braga, R. Gomes, M. Alves, F. Mirza, V. Ciriello, G. Carrozza, P. Oliveira, and V. Cahill, "Emmon: A wsn system architecture for large scale and dense real-time embedded monitoring," in *Embedded and Ubiquitous Computing (EUC), 2011 IFIP 9th International Conference on*. IEEE, 2011, pp. 150–157.
- [22] N. Enterprises, "Nagios," <https://exchange.nagios.org/directory>, 2017.
- [23] OpenStack-Wiki, "Ceilometer," 2017.
- [24] R. Olups, *Zabbix 1.8 network monitoring*. Packt Publishing Ltd, 2010.
- [25] S. Pfleeger and R. Cunningham, "Why measuring security is hard," *IEEE Security & Privacy*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 46–54, 2010.
- [26] W. Jansen, "Research directions in security metrics," *Journal of Information System Security*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 3–22, 2011.
- [27] T. Phinney, "Iec 62443: Industrial network and system security," *Last accessed July*, vol. 29, 2013.
- [28] I. IEC, "61508 functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems," *International electrotechnical commission*, 1998.
- [29] S. Maksuti, A. Bicaku, M. Tauber, S. Palkovits-Rauter, S. Haas, and J. Delsing, "Towards flexible and secure end-to-end communication in industry 4.0," in *IEEE 15th International Conference of Industrial Informatics INDIN'2017*, 2017.
- [30] A. Bicaku, S. Maksuti, S. Palkovits-Rauter, M. Tauber, R. Matischek, C. Schmittner, G. Mantas, M. Thron, and J. Delsing, "Towards trustworthy end-to-end communication in industry 4.0," in *IEEE 15th International Conference of Industrial Informatics INDIN'2017*, 2017.
- [31] F. Blomstedt, "Arrowhead test tool," https://forge.soa4d.org/plugins/scmgit/cgi-bin/gitweb.cgi?p=arrowhead-f/arrowhead-f.git;a=blob;f=5_Compliance/1_Testtool/Arrowhead_SysD_Compliance+Test+Tool.pdf;h=f36e1b1cf63c5a05c79307a10d506739f15d9f4c;hb=HEAD.